

"SOME BIOCHEMICAL ANALYZES OF *SPIRULINA* BIOMASS"

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Abstract Recently, much attention has been paid to phytopreparations in pharmaceutical technology. This group of medicines includes plant extracts containing a complex of biologically active compounds with a wide spectrum of action, good tolerability and a low risk of adverse reactions. In this regard, the purpose of this study was to study the effect of the extractant on the component composition of chlorella extract and to develop qualitative methods of analysis. The conducted studies have shown that extracts obtained with the help of various extractants from biomass *C vulgaris* strains C-2019, C-11, C-16, C-98 contain a wide range of biologically active compounds, such as flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids, glycosides and saponins. Qualitative reactions were carried out on the main biologically active compounds, which can later be used to confirm the quality of chlorella extracts.

Keywords: *microalgae, Chlorella vulgaris, qualitative reactions, flavonoids, tannins.*

Introduction

SPIRULINA (*Spirulina*), a genus of cyanobacteria. The foliate thallus is formed by single or film-like unbranched, spirally twisted filaments (trichomes) capable of active rotational motion. Cells with poorly discernible transverse walls, without air vesicles, with thylakoids located parallel to the longitudinal axis of the cell. C. multiplication is associated with the fragmentation of trichomes and the formation of groups of cells (gormogonia) capable of movement. Ok. 50 types; they live in fresh, not heavily polluted water bodies, in detritus among aquatic plants, in

coastal marine and brackish waters; some prefer thermal and mineral waters. *C. cells* are rich in protein. *S. platensis* (in Africa) and *S. maxima* (in Mexico) has long been used by the local population for food; cultivated for food protein.

The main visible advantage of microalgae over other organisms is that they are photoautotrophs and therefore do not require organic matter to grow, hence their large-scale cultivation is theoretically easier and cheaper. Microalgae are used in various industries such as food, cosmetic, nutraceutical, medical, pharmaceutical and agricultural. They synthesize secondary metabolites to protect against other microorganisms. In this regard, these compounds can be used to combat infectious diseases.

Most of the macro- and microelements contained in the biomass of *Spirulina platensis* are in the form of organic compounds. In particular, trace elements - cations of d-elements form chelate complexes with amino acids and polypeptides.

Proteins are a significant group of biologically active compounds of *Spirulina platensis* biomass due to their high content and balanced amino acid composition. According to various literature sources, the protein content in the biomass of *Spirulina platensis* is 40–70%. Such scatter of data is associated with the use of different methods of quantitative analysis, different strains, and differences in cultivation conditions. Studies have shown that with the age of the culture, the relative protein content in it decreases, although certain fluctuations are observed throughout the entire cultivation period.

Studies of the fractional composition of proteins by the electrophoretic method made it possible to establish the presence of a large number of protein fractions and their certain variability. There are both stable protein fractions that are found throughout the growth of the culture, and variable protein fractions that appear only at certain periods of culture growth. *Spirulina platensis* carbohydrates are

mainly represented by complex polymers. Polysaccharides are part of cells, cell walls, and mucous membranes.

In *Spirulina platensis*, as well as other blue-green algae, polysaccharides such as hemicelluloses and pectin substances predominate over all fractions of carbohydrates (10–16%).

The blue-green microalga *Spirulina platensis*, unlike other plants and bacteria, contains water-soluble phycobilin pigments — C-phycoerythrin and allophycoerythrin.

Research methods and principles

The object of the study was the air-dry biomass of strains *Chlorella vulgaris* Beyerinck IGF C-2019, C-11, C-16 and C-98, grown by the deep method on Tamiya medium at a 16-hour photoperiod and a temperature of 28-30°C. The dried *Chlorella* biomass was subjected to pretreatment with organic solvents at a temperature of 60°C for 20 min using a reflux condenser, followed by evaporation of the solvent. A mixture of ethanol–acetone–sulphuric ether (1:4:10) was used as a solvent. To obtain extracts, 5 extractants were used: ethyl alcohol 95%, acetone (chemically pure), petroleum ether (chemically pure), hexane (chemically pure) and heptane (chemically pure). The obtained extracts for further use were stored at a temperature of 2 to 4°C. Then they were examined for the presence of tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids, saponins, glycosides and alkaloids.

Main results

The biomass of four strains of *Chlorella vulgaris* was extracted with five different solvents. Phytochemicals present in microalgae extracts have been identified as flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids, glycosides and saponins (see Table 1). All extracts of microalgae contained flavonoids in their composition. It is known that reactions to flavonoids are based on the formation of colored complex compounds. The cyanidin test (Shinoda test) was used as the main specific reaction for flavonoids.

Table 1 - Phytochemical analysis of various extracts of *Chlorella vulgaris*

Strain C. vulgaris	Extract	Tannins	Flavonoids	Terpenoids	Glycosides	Alkaloids	Saponins
C- 2019	Acetone	++	++	-	++	-	-
	Alcoholic	+++	+++	+	+	-	+
	Heptane	++	++	-	-	+	-
	Hexane	++	+	-	+	+	-
	Petrolejny	++	+++	+	-	+	+
C - 11	Acetone	++	++	-	+	+	-
	Alcoholic	+++	+	-	+	-	-
	Heptane	++	+	++	+	-	-
	Hexane	++	++	-	+	-	-
	Petrolejny	+	++	++	-	-	-
C - 16	Acetone	++	+	-	+	-	-
	Alcoholic	+++	+	+	-	-	+
	Heptane	++	++	+	-	+	-
	Hexane	+	+	-	-	+	-
	Petrolejny	++	++	-	+	-	-
C - 98	Acetone	+	+	-	+	-	-
	Alcoholic	+++	+	-	-	-	+
	Heptane	+	++	-	-	-	-
	Hexane	+	+	-	+	+	-
	Petrolejny	++	++	+	-	+	-

Note: High concentration (+++), Moderate concentration (++) , Low concentration (+) and absence (-)

Flavonoids were the predominant phytochemicals and were found in all extracts obtained with various extractants. The highest levels of content were

observed in alcohol and petroleum extracts of strain C-2019. Also, tannins were present in all extracts of microalgae.

Basically, alkaloids were present in heptane extracts, and saponins in alcohol extracts. Terpenoids and glycosides were found in biomass extracts of strain C-11.

Conclusion

Studies of extracts obtained using various extractants from the biomass of *C. vulgaris* strains C-2019, C-11, C-16, C-98 showed that the studied solutions contain a wide range of biologically active compounds: flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids, glycosides and saponins. The tests carried out on these compounds can be used to confirm the quality of chlorella extracts.

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